

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

How important is crop rotation to the arable crops cultivation?

In agriculture, crop rotation is an important practice that involves the sequential or alternating cultivation of different crops in a field. Crop rotation helps preserve and improve soil fertility and its structure. Growing deep-rooted crops between those with shallower root systems aerates the soil deeply and enriches the lower soil horizons with carbon, creating favorable conditions for both subsequent crops and microbial activity. Today, in a highly variable weather conditions, crop rotation is also beneficial in alleviating drought damage. Following crop rotation helps maintain a balanced level of organic matter in the soil, which is created through the activity of living organisms in the soil and represents organic material at various stages of decomposition. An adequate amount of soil organic matter

improves the soil's water retention capacity and contributes to the preservation of soil structure. The alleviation of all the aforementioned deficiencies can be aided by implementing crop rotation that is in accordance with soil conditions. For example, it is possible to increase the humus stock in the soil by 2 tons per hectare when a two-year clover or meadow grass rotation is used. When incorporating one-year legume straw into the soil, the humus stock increases by 0.4 tons per hectare annually, and when cultivating cover crops, it can increase by up to 0.2-0.3 tons per hectare per year. Generally, it can be estimated that applying 5 tons of straw to the soil can restore 1 ton of humus. In our region, farmers use both the cultivation of one-year legume crops and plowing straw into the soil on their fields.

1. Annual legumes on conventional-tillage field, nemoral region case study no 12. Photo Shanskiy, M.

2. Cereal straw will be ploughed in at the organic fields in the fall, nemoral region case study no 12. Photo Shanskiy, M.

KEYWORDS

Crop rotation, soil fertility, nemoral region

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